

A THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPT OF INVENTION RIGHTS AND TRENDS IN THEIR DEVELOPMENT

Vakhobjonov Dilmurod Dilshodbek o'g'li

Independent Researcher at the Academy of

Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19603835>

Abstract: This article provides a theoretical analysis of the concept of rights to an invention. It highlights the importance of inventions in the development of society, the fundamental principles of patent law, and its legal nature. The article also analyzes the exclusive right of the patent holder, the balance between public and private interests, the patenting process, and the role of inventions within the intellectual property system. The author substantiates the need to improve the legal mechanisms for the protection of inventions.

Keywords: invention, patent law, intellectual property, exclusive right, patent monopoly, legal protection, innovation, industrial property, technology, legal mechanisms

In the modern era, innovative development and technological progress are of vital importance in all spheres of public life. Inventions, in turn, manifest as the main driving force of this process, playing a significant role in economic growth, increasing production efficiency, and simplifying human life. Therefore, the legal protection of inventions, the clear definition of the rights related to them, and the formation of effective legal mechanisms are among the most pressing tasks.

It is well known that inventions play a crucial role in human development and social progress. It is precisely through inventive activity that new technologies, products, and processes are created, manual labor is eased, and various economic and social problems are effectively resolved. For this reason, defining the legal status of inventions, developing the legislation concerning them, and improving law enforcement practices are urgent matters.

Throughout its historical development, the procedure for inventions has also been based on the principle of "exclusive right": the right holder is granted a preferential right for a specific period, while others are only given the opportunity to use the invention. This mechanism serves to ensure a balance between fostering inventions and deriving social benefit from them.

The rapid development and global diffusion of new technologies raise the issue of fully ensuring the interests of all parties. The main problem is that some invention rights holders achieve substantial financial or strategic benefits, while others may remain constrained by legal boundaries. From this perspective, a "golden bridge" of interests—that is, a mechanism that ensures a balance of rights and benefits for all parties—is crucial.

Although at first glance it may seem that industrial property rights are regulated within the framework of intellectual property legislation, the effective regulation of relations associated with practical development and the creation of new technologies requires the improvement of legislative and legal mechanisms. The processes of registering, patenting, and protecting inventions are of primary importance from this viewpoint.

The patent law system is composed of fundamental principles, one of the most important of which is the recognition of the patent holder's exclusive right to use the patented object. Only the patent holder has the right to introduce the patented invention into civil circulation through manufacturing, using, importing, selling, and other means. Other persons must refrain from its

unauthorized use, and the patent holder, in turn, has the ability to demand this right. It follows that other persons must refrain from infringing upon the patent holder's exclusive right. Any infringement not provided for by contract or law must be stopped, and the infringer shall be subject to the sanctions established by law.

The next principle of patent law is the recognition of the patent monopoly and its protection on a global scale. This does not preclude the function of protecting public interests; that is, it requires coordinating the interests of the patent holder on the one hand and society on the other. One of the main manifestations of this is limiting the patent's term of validity to a specified period.[1] At the same time, the creator must make a genuine contribution to the state of the art, which is a condition for granting patent protection to a specific invention. To this end, the claimed solutions are examined, and conditions are created for interested parties to familiarize themselves with the latest developments. Furthermore, based on public interest, the law also defines cases of so-called "free use" of patented inventions.

The third principle is that protection is granted only to developments that are formally and legally recognized. This requires preparing a special application and submitting it to the authorized body (the Department of Intellectual Property). This application is reviewed in accordance with the established procedure and is approved if it meets the requirements of the law.

Patent law protects new technical and design solutions, as well as new plant varieties and new animal breeds. Unlike copyright, patent law protects ideas—specifically, the technical, artistic, and other essences of an object that can be repeatedly reused in various forms. For this reason, a patent is generally more valuable than the exclusive right to a work. On the other hand, patent law is one of the most complex institutions of intellectual property, as registering and protecting a patent requires knowledge not only in the field of law but also in the relevant technical field.

Before delving into patent law, it is appropriate to define the concept of a patent itself. A patent (from the Latin *patens* – open, clear, evident) is a document confirming state recognition of a technical solution or invention and the inventor's exclusive right to their invention. It is generally a document guaranteeing legal protection by the state in exchange for the disclosure of the invention by the inventor, utility model author, industrial design author, or the author of a new plant variety or animal breed. A patent is a document that certifies an author's exclusive right to something, such as a discovery, an innovation, or a model of production equipment, and its main function is to protect the author's intellectual rights. Patent law is also recognized and protected in Islamic jurisprudence.[2]

The process of obtaining a patent, as well as the responsibilities and rights of the patent holder, vary from country to country. The exclusive rights granted to a patent holder prevent others (third parties) from making, using, selling, or distributing the patented invention without permission.

Patents are the most common form of intellectual property protection, providing legal protection not only for a specific invented machine or process but also for variations of that machine or the underlying processes on which it may be based.[3]

Furthermore, patents are a primary tool for companies to maximize the benefits of new and innovative ideas and technologies. It is no secret that in the modern knowledge-based economy, an innovative company's patent strategy is a key component of its business strategy. Original inventions and ideas are the driving force of our modern economy. The management of

knowledge resources, especially new ideas and concepts, is crucial for any company's ability to transform, adapt, and capitalize on new opportunities in the competitive, rapidly changing business environment. A single innovation born from an innovative idea can lead to astonishing success or change the future of companies on the verge of bankruptcy, as proven by financial giants such as Apple and the Fortune 500.

In our country, the practice of working with patents is not yet well-developed. Companies in other countries are actively engaged with patents—they are vigorously buying and selling them, creating patent pools, using patents and trademarks in company capitalization, and bringing their products to market or indirectly competing with goods and services in foreign markets. The U.S. even patents business methods and software.[4]

It is common to consider many legal concepts in an objective sense (as a body of legal norms) and a subjective sense (as the right of a specific subject). In an objective sense, patent law is a civil-law institution that regulates exclusive and other property and personal non-property relations associated with recognizing authorship, protecting inventions, utility models, industrial designs, and selection achievements, as well as determining their use, providing material and moral incentives, and protecting rights.

In a subjective sense, patent law is the exclusive and other proprietary or personal non-property right of a specific subject pertaining to a particular invention, utility model, industrial design, or selection achievement.[5]

In a broad sense, patent law, in addition to design and technical solutions, also encompasses relations connected with the creation of biological solutions. In academia, there is a viewpoint that trademarks and rationalization proposals also belong to the objects of patent law.[6]

The advantages of patent protection in a formalized form and, consequently, with greater certainty, have led to the fact that some copyright objects have the possibility of legal protection according to the above principles (objects of dual protection at the discretion of the copyright owner). These are objects that are the result of artistic and technical creation.

Artistic and technical creativity is creative activity in the field of industrial design with the aim of "improving the external characteristics of objects produced in the industrial sector." A protected result of artistic and technical creativity is an industrial design.

The specifics of legal protection for the results of technical creativity led to the formation of the independent institute of the sub-sector of intellectual law—"patent law."

The system of patent law can be revealed through the features of individual elements of patent legal relations: subjects, objects, and components.

The subjects of patent law are the author—the person who created the technical or design solution whose creative work is protected; the patent holder—the person to whom the exclusive right belongs; third parties refusing to use the patent without the consent of the patent holder; and the patent office (the Intellectual Property Agency under the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan) authorized to make decisions on granting and refusing to grant a patent.

The objects of patent rights are technical solutions (inventions and utility models), artistic solutions (industrial designs), and a new plant variety or animal breed (breeding achievements).

A concession is a document certifying the granting of an exclusive right to profit from one's industrial invention and a monopoly on prohibiting others from duplicating and using that invention[7]. The earliest form of patents existed around 500 BC in the Greek city of Sibaris,

where chefs received a 1-year monopoly on newly created types of dishes. Some even suggest that patents originated where guilds existed in the Roman Empire. In the Middle Ages, guilds developed under the conditions of a market economy that existed in cities. It is likely that the ownership relationship was developed to protect craft knowledge, which enjoyed widespread prestige outside the region, thereby increasing the commercial value of the craft. Thus, it can be viewed as communal property rather than a monopoly exercised by an individual. The craft developed in the guild and was shared by all the masters of the guild. For example, Venetian glassmakers became famous for their glass production during the Renaissance. Glassmaking was restricted to guild members only and was strictly controlled by them. There were rules about working days, apprenticeship, technical specifications, glass quality, ingredients used. As the prestige of their crafts grew, so did their commercial value, while it was understood that the export of these crafts to other parts of Europe should be strictly prohibited. Thus, the earliest forms of monopoly emerged in the form of communal property, which was limited to the region and the guild.

The history of patent law begins with the privileges granted to inventions that emerged in the late Middle Ages. Initially, privileges were a monopoly granted at the monarch's discretion and serving the interests of a specific person or organization. At the same time, a patent for an invention could be obtained not by the inventor personally, but by anyone who had paid enough money for the patent. Nevertheless, during the period of rapid industrial development, people did not stop inventing. And so, the world's first patent for an invention was granted in 1421 by the Florentine city council in the name of Filippo Brunelleschi, who invented the ship's turning crane. The decision to grant a patent for the architect's invention was made on June 9, 1421, and is considered the first regulatory document in the history of patent law. This decision recognized the rights of inventors to intellectual property and contained an established incentive mechanism recognized in modern patent law. The oldest British patent was granted in 1449 by Henry VI to John of Fleming of Eton College for inventing the manufacture of stained glass. The word patent in its modern interpretation originated in the Republic of Venice in 1474. The Venetian Senate created the first patent law, reflecting the concept of intellectual property and demonstrating the importance of protecting the rights of inventors. In addition to the rights of the inventor, this law included important issues such as the mechanism of incentives, compensation for violation of rights, and the term of protection. The law of Venice is cited as the foundation of modern international patent statutes. Craig Nard, director of the Intellectual Property Center at Western Reserve University in Ohio (USA), called the law "a great achievement in the Venetian Renaissance." Everything we hold dear in today's patent system can be found in this Venetian statute."^[8] In the same year, a decision was made to notify the republic's government of inventions implemented in practice to prevent counterfeiting. According to the decision, the validity period of the patent is set at 10 years. During that period, the royal government protected the rights of inventors by granting "personal privileges," the prototype of the modern patent. The purpose of these privileges was to free the inventor from the control of the manufacturer. Between 1561 and 1610, Queen Elizabeth herself granted approximately 50 patents to rights holders to exercise a monopoly on production and trade. During the reigns of Elizabeth I and her successor, King James I, the royal court granted monopoly patents on well-crafted tools or items (vinegar and playing cards) to replenish the royal treasury. This situation caused some civil unrest, and the administration of patents was transferred to common law courts. In 1624, the Statute of Monopolies was promulgated in

England, according to which patents began to be issued for new invention projects. James I was forced to revoke all previously granted patents, and existing ideas and inventions were declared to be in the public domain. A strict 14-year monopoly period was established for the invention[9]. This regulation resulted in a decline in the royal powers that had governed English patent law for more than two centuries, and served as the basis for the modern British patent system, as well as a model for U.S. Patent Law.

The Statute of Monopolies was an almost dramatic turning point for patent law, practice, and policy. The Charter was one of the culminations of the ongoing struggle against the abuse of power by the royal government and was a significant declaratory measure restricting royal rights. However, the implementation of this regulation into practice turned into a century-long process. Nevertheless, this Statute of Monopolies was important in future legal and political discussions of patents.[10]

Since 1624, the king established special privileges—patents—for individuals engaged in the production of industrial products based on imported technology. Individuals using such a new technology had exclusive rights to use it for the long period of time it took to master it. As a result of the exclusive right, the patent holder also used some privileges in the fight against competition for the purpose of incentivizing the development of a new product[11]. Since then, the patent system has been improved in many ways and has been established as a legal instrument regulating relations regarding the creation of new industrial products and the transfer of technology to others. The first court cases in the field of patent protection for inventors also took place in England. In the judgment of the Ipswich Textile Masters case, it was stated: "If anyone in the kingdom has created a new invention and manufacture at the risk of his life and wealth, then he is granted by the king's grace the right to use the invention only to compensate the inventor for his own funds and efforts." After the patent expired, the king did not take responsibility for restoring the right of re-ownership."[12] The first American Patent Act appeared on April 10, 1790, a year after the Constitution was ratified. According to the act, "useful, important, and new" inventions were granted patent protection for 14 years, and in addition, all patent applications were made mandatory to be supplemented with a full description of the invention. On the basis of this act, on July 30, 1790, Samuel Hopkins patented the method for obtaining potassium carbonate. Amendments were made to this Act in 1793 (products and methods that serve to improve an existing invention also became patentable) and 1836 (the examination of novelty began during the examination process, and now a new application from the previous inventor is accepted only if the components of the previous invention are used in a new way). In the United States, between 1790 and 1836, fewer than 10,000 patents were issued under this act. With this, successive patent laws were adopted in developed countries, including the first patent law in France on January 7, 1791, in Spain in 1820, in Russia in 1870, and in Germany in 1877. In Japan, as in many other continental European countries, the first patents appeared in the 19th century. Throughout the 20th century, the use of the patent system acquired a universal character for all countries. As production developed and improved, the patent system also changed. The concept of a patentable invention has undergone significant changes. While patents were initially granted for any new technical means useful to industry, by the mid-19th century, a lack of criteria for inventions began to be felt, and in many countries, primarily in the USA, another requirement was introduced—*invention creativity*. In 1849, the U.S. Patent Act expanded the requirements for patentability, and now an invention is recognized as an invention if it is not obvious to

specialists in a specific field from information regarding the level of technical progress. This is currently an important feature of patentable inventions in all developed and some developing countries. The content of this requirement also remained unchanged[13].

The protection of intellectual property rights first became a global issue when inventors refused to participate in the International Exhibition of Inventions held in Vienna in 1873. In this context, the first international treaty on the protection of interstate intellectual property rights was adopted in 1883—the Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property—and shortly thereafter, in 1886, the Bern Convention for the Protection of Works of Art was signed in the field of copyright. In 1893, the first organization for the protection of intellectual property, the International Bureau, was established based on the Paris and Bern Conventions. In 1967, the International Bureau for the Protection of Intellectual Property was transformed into the World Intellectual Property Organization. In conclusion, the first manifestations of property rights and the protection of human capital appeared in the 5th century, and over time, human developments began to take on a modern appearance. Today, inventions have become an integral part of our lives. Databases of patent documents and the patent fund. The State Patent Fund was established in 1993 under the Republican Territorial Patent Fund, which began its collection in 1966 and has become one of the largest patent funds in terms of the volume and scope of patent documentation within its structure. The main sources of the state fund for patent documentation are international exchange, patent documentation, ownership of methodological literature, and subscriptions to periodicals. The fund is presented in printed form and on optical discs. Currently, the PHDF is the only fund in the Republic of Uzbekistan that fully collects patent documents, and as a central structure where patent documents of our country and foreign countries are stored, it contains patent documents from 25 countries of the world, 2 international and 2 regional organizations, literature on inventions and patent law. The fund contains about 79 million documents, the majority of which (64.5 million) are displayed on optical discs. The fund contains applications for inventions, copyrights, patents, descriptions of utility models, descriptions of industrial designs, official bulletins, reference journals, methodological and regulatory literature, and reference documents. The collection contains descriptions of inventions, author's certificates, and descriptions of patents issued in the Russian Federation registered in Uzbekistan from 1924 to 1993. Along with full descriptions of inventions, the fund also contains official bulletins from leading foreign countries and CIS countries. These bulletins contain information on national applications and patents, utility models, industrial designs, including bibliographic data and an abstract of the invention, service marks and registered utility models, computer programs and databases, breeding achievements, as well as information on all legal changes in the status of patents. The library's collection includes encyclopedias in all fields and fields of science, as well as dictionaries in Uzbek, Russian, English, French, German, Italian, Spanish, Ancient Greek, Persian, Afghan, Czech, Japanese, Polish, Serbo-Croatian, Korean, and Turkish.

References:

1. Zaxarova K.V. Ponyatiye i osnovopolagayushiye prinsipi patentnogo prava // Interaktivnaya nauka. 2022. №10 (75). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ponyatie-i-osnovopolagayuschie-printsipy-patentnogo-prava> (data obrasheniya: 24.11.2025).

2. Islom moliyasi. Islomda aql-zakovat, mualliflik va nomoddiy boyliklarga ega bo'lgan huquq [Elektron resurs] islommoliyasi.uz. 06.07.2020.
3. Jeffrey I. Auerbach. Patent law principles and strategies. – USA, 2006. – 30 p.
4. Iroda Yoqubova. Intellektual mulk – innovatsion rivojlanishning zaruriy omili. Yangi O'zbekiston. 6-noyabr 2020-yil. [Elektron resurs] yuz.uz/news.
5. N.M. Korshunov, N.D. Eriashvili, Yu.S. Xaritonova. Patentnoye pravo: ucheb. posobiye dlya studentov, obuchayushixsya po spetsialnoti "Yurisprudensiya". Pod redaksiyey N.M. Korshunova. – M., Zakon i pravo, 2012. – S.159.
6. Antimonov B.S., Fleyshis Ye.A. Izobretatelskoye pravo. – M., 1960; Izobretatelskoye pravo: Uchebnik / Otv. red. N.V. Mironov. M., 1986; Zenin I.A. Pravo intellektualnoy sobstvennosti: Uchebnik dlya magistrrov. – M.: Yurayt, 2014.
7. Pravo intellektualnoy sobstvennosti. Patentnoye pravo: Uchebnik. T.4. // Ppod obsh. red. L.A. Novoselovoy. Moskovskiy Gosudarstvenniy Yuridicheskiy Universitet Imeni O.Ye. Kutafina. – M.: Statut, 2019. – S.659.
8. History and evolution of patent law – international & national perspectives. Karnika Seth, Attorney at law & Partner, Seth Associates. URL: <http://www.karnikaseth.com/wp-content/uploads/history-and-evolution-of-patents1.pdf>
9. Matt Kwong. Six significant moments in patent history. An article created by Public relations department of Thomson Reuters Intellectual Property & Science division, and Reuters Brand Content Solutions. URL: <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-moments-patent-idUSKBN0IN1Y120141104>
10. Owning Ideas: Chapter I: Patents English and Colonial Origins. URL: <https://law.utexas.edu/faculty/obracha/dissertation/pdf/chapter1.pdf>
11. Oqyulov O. Intellektual mulk huquqi. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Fanlar Akademiyasi A I. Mo'minov nomidagi falsafa va huquq instituti. – T. 2005. – 40 b.
12. N.M. Korshunov, N.D. Eriashvili, Yu.S. Xaritonova. Patentnoye pravo: ucheb. posobiye dlya studentov, obuchayushixsya po spetsialnoti "Yurisprudensiya". Pod redaksiyey N.M. Korshunova. – M., 2012. – S.159.
13. A.P. Abramenko. Osnovi patentovedeniya. Uchebno-metodicheskoye posobiye. – Pavlodar, Pavlodarskiy universitet, 2004. – S. 100.

